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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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LOGISTIKA AUTSORSINGI TURLARI

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Annotatsiya: Logistika sohasida autsorsing o'z faoliyatini optimallashtirish va xarajatlarni kamaytirishga intilayotgan kompaniyalar uchun muhim strategiyalardan biri hisoblanadi. Ushbu maqola uchinchi tomon logistikasi (3PL), to'rtinchi tomon logistikasi (4PL) va yuk tashish kabi logistika sohasida autsorsingning turli ko'rinishlarini o'rganadi. Maqolada, shuningdek, O'zbekiston logistika sektorida autsorsingning ortib borayotgan ahamiyati muhokama qilinib, xalqaro va o'zbekistonlik tadqiqotchilarning fikrlari yoritilgan. Mavjud adabiyotlarni ko'rib chiqish orqali ushbu maqola turli xil autsorsing modellari ta'minot zanjirlarining samaradorligi va moslashuvchanligiga qanday hissa qo'shishini aniq tushunishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: logistika, autsorsing, uchinchi tomon logistikasi (3PL), to'rtinchi tomon logistikasi (4PL), yuk tashish, ta'minot zanjiri boshqaruvi.

Аннотация: Аутсорсинг в сфере логистики является одной из важных стратегий для компаний, стремящихся оптимизировать свою деятельность и сократить расходы. В этой статье рассматриваются различные формы логистического аутсорсинга, такие как сторонняя логистика (3PL), сторонняя логистика (4PL) и экспедирование грузов. В статье также рассматривается растущая значимость аутсорсинга в логистической сфере Узбекистана и освещаются мнения международных и узбекских исследователей. Посредством обзора существующей литературы данная статья призвана получить четкое понимание того, как различные модели аутсорсинга способствуют эффективности и гибкости цепочек поставок.

Ключевые слова: логистика, аутсорсинг, сторонняя логистика (3PL), сторонняя логистика (4PL), доставка, управление цепочками поставок.

Abstrakt: Outsourcing in logistics is one of the important strategies for companies seeking to optimize their operations and reduce costs. This article explores the various forms of logistics outsourcing, such as third-party logistics (3PL), fourth-party logistics (4PL), and freight forwarding. The article also discusses the growing importance of outsourcing in the logistics sector of Uzbekistan and highlights the opinions of international and Uzbek researchers. Through a review of existing literature, this paper aims to gain a clear understanding of how different outsourcing models contribute to the efficiency and flexibility of supply chains.

Keywords: logistics, outsourcing, third-party logistics (3PL), fourth-party logistics (4PL), shipping, supply chain management.

Kirish

O‘zbekistonda davlat sektoriga outsorsing faoliyatini olib borishda huquqiy asoslar yaratilib kelinmoqda. Bunga ta’lim va tarbiya tizimining barcha bo‘g‘inlari faoliyatining bugungi zamon talablari asosida takomillashtirish asosiy vazifa qilib belgilanganligidan kelib chiqqan holda bu va boshqa sohalar misolida outsorsingning davlat sektorida qo‘llashning afzalliklariga to‘xtalib o‘tiladi.

Autsorsingning davlat sektorida qo‘llashda ijtimoiy xizmat darajasining keskin pasayishiga yo‘l qo‘ymaslik choralari ko‘riladi, inson uchun o‘ta muhim, yuqori kaloriyali oziq-ovqat iste‘moli tarkibi takomillashtiriladi, inson genofondini saqlash uchun homilador ayollar va bolalarning ovqatlanish ratsioni bo‘yicha amaldagi me‘yorlarni xalqaro standartlar asosida qayta ko‘rib chiqilishiga olib keladi.

Bundan bir necha yillar ilgari «outsorsing» mexanizmi faqat xususiy sektorda foydalanilgan bo‘lsa, bugungi kunda budjet tashkilotlarida ham ijtimoiy xizmat ko‘rsatishda «outsorsing»dan unumli foydalanilmoqda.

Autsorsing (outsourcing) – tashkilotning u yoki yoki funksiyalarini shu faoliyatni olib borishga ixtisoslashgan tashqi ijro etuvchilarga berishdir. Boshqacha qilib aytganda, outsorsing deganda, davlat sektorining nodavlat sektordan tovarlar, ishlar va xizmatlar sotib olishining umumiy hajmi tushuniladi.

Davlat muassasalarida outsorsing usulida ovqatlantirish «Davlat xaridlari to‘g‘risida»gi O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Qonuniga muvofiq tarkibi tasdiqlanadigan Tanlov komissiyasi tomonidan o‘tkaziladigan tanlov asosida tashkil etiladi.

O‘zbekistonda xususiy sektorda yaxshi tajribadan o‘tgan zamonaviy mexanizm va uslublarni budjet xizmati ko‘rsatilayotgan ijtimoiy sohalarida qo‘llanishi, davlat sektorida outsorsing usulini joriy etishda xarajatlarning tejalishi va xizmat sifati yaxshilanishining muhim ahamiyatga egaligi, davlat sektori muassasalarida misol uchun sog‘lom ratsional va xavfsiz ovqatlanishni tashkil etilishini takomillashtirish, keytring (yuqori darajada umumiy ovqatlanish), ularning kombinatlari kabi zamonaviy usullardan foydalanilish, outsorser bilan davlat muassasalari o‘rtasida outsorsingga oid shartnomalar tuzilishiga huquqiy asoslarning mavjudligi, ijtimoiy sohada outsorsing asosida xarajatlarning natijadorligi outsorsingdan foydalanishning afzalliklari bo‘lib hisoblanadi.

Autsorsing shartnomalari xususiy sektor vakillari bilan O‘zbekiston Respublikasining fuqarolik qonunchiligi va xo‘jalik yurituvchi sub‘ektlar faoliyatini tartibga soluvchi qator qonunlar va qonun osti hujjatlari bilan tartibga solinadi. Bunga outsorsing shartnomasi erkin tuziladi va hech qanday rasmiy talablar o‘rnatilmagan.

Autsorsingga oid shartnomalar davlat sektori muassasalari bilan tuzilganda O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining qaror va

farmoyishlari hamda tarmoqlar vazirliklarining qaror va buyruqlari bilan tartibga solinadi.

Shuning uchun davlat sektoriga tegishli outsorsing shartnomasini tuzishda O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining va tarmoq vazirliklarining qarorlari bilan tasdiqlangan nizomlarida qo'yilgan talablar asosida amalga oshiriladi.

Outsorsing turlari. Outsorsingning quyidagi (asosiy) turlari keng tarqalgan: buxgalterlik, yuridik, kadrlar bo'yicha, IT outsorsing, binoni yig'ishtirish (klining), ko'chmas mulk ob'ektlaridan foydalanish outsorsingi, logistik yoki transport outsorsingi, xodimlar outsorsingi.

Outsorsing tamoyili: "O'zimdagi faqatgina boshqalardan yaxshiroq bajara oladiganimni qoldiraman, tashqi bajaruvchiga u boshqalardan yaxshiroq bajara oladiganini beraman".

Zamonaviy biznes muhitida kompaniyalar samaradorlikni oshirish, xarajatlarni kamaytirish va asosiy vazifalarga e'tibor qaratish borasida doimiy qiyinchiliklarga duch kelmoqdalar. Ushbu maqsadlarga erishishning eng samarali usullaridan biri outsorsing amaliyotini qo'llashdir. Outsorsing – bu ma'lum funksiyalar yoki vazifalarni ixtisoslashgan tashqi tashkilotlarga ishonib topshirish jarayoni bo'lib, u kompaniyalarga o'z asosiy faoliyatlariga ko'proq e'tibor qaratish va resurslarni tejash imkonini beradi. Logistikada outsorsing deganda, kompaniyalarga asosiy biznes faoliyatiga diqqat qaratish imkonini beruvchi transport, omborxonalar va tarqatish kabi muayyan vazifalarni bajarish uchun tashqi tashkilotlar bilan shartnoma tuzish amaliyoti tushuniladi. Ushbu strategiya, ayniqsa, ta'minot zanjirini boshqarishda foydali ekanligini isbotlaydi, chunki bu firmalarga logistika xizmatlarini yetkazib beruvchilarning tajribasi va resurslaridan foydalanish imkonini beradi. Infratuzilmasini faol ravishda takomillashtirib borayotgan va sanoat bazasini kengaytirayotgan barcha davlatlar kabi, O'zbekistonda ham logistika sohasida outsorsing amaliyoti joriy qilina boshlandi. Mamlakat iqtisodiyoti o'sib borayotgani va uning jahon bozorlari bilan aloqasi oshgani sayin, kompaniyalar ta'minot zanjirlarining murakkabliklarini boshqarish uchun outsorsingga murojaat qilmoqdalar. Ushbu maqolada logistika sohasida outsorsing turlari, ularning afzalliklari va O'zbekiston sharoitiga mosligi muhokama qilinadi. Outsorsing faqat logistik bilan cheklanib qolmasdan, boshqa sohalarda jumladan tovar aylanmasi, dasturlash kabi soxalarda ham keng qo'llaniladi. Masalan, dasturlashda outsorsing bugungi kunda keng tarqalgan amaliyotlardan biri hisoblanadi. Ko'plab kompaniyalar dasturiy ta'minotlarni ishlab chiqish, texnik xizmat ko'rsatish yoki IT xizmatlarini tashqi provayderlarga topshirish orqali o'z ichki resurslarini samarali boshqarish imkoniga ega bo'lmoqdalar. Bu, nafaqat ishlab chiqarish va logistika sohasida, balki axborot texnologiyalari sohasida ham samaradorlik va tezkorlikni ta'minlash imkonini beradi. Shuningdek, tovar aylanmasida outsorsingni qo'llash ham bugungi kunda keng tarqalgan amaliyotlardan biriga aylandi.

Bugungi kunda biznes jarayonlarini optimallashtirish va samaradorlikni oshirish maqsadida ko'plab kompaniyalar logistika outsorsingidan foydalanmoqda. **Logistika outsorsingi** – bu tashqi kompaniyalarga logistika operatsiyalarini ishonib topshirish jarayonidir. Ushbu xizmat kompaniyalarga xarajatlarni kamaytirish, xizmat sifatini yaxshilash va asosiy biznes faoliyatiga e'tibor qaratish imkoniyatini beradi.

Logistika outsorsingining asosiy turlari

1. **3PL (Third-Party Logistics) – Uchinchi tomon logistika xizmatlari**
3PL modeli kompaniyaga yuk tashish, omborxonalar xizmatlari, bo'jxona rasmiylashtiruv va boshqa logistika operatsiyalarini tashqi provayderga topshirish imkonini beradi. Ushbu model ko'pincha kichik va o'rta bizneslar tomonidan qo'llaniladi.

2. **4PL (Fourth-Party Logistics) – To'rtinchi tomon logistika xizmatlari**
4PL provayderlari 3PL kompaniyalaridan farqli ravishda butun logistika jarayonini boshqaradi, ya'ni strategik rejalashtirish, tahlil va optimallashtirishni amalga oshiradi. Ular mijoz kompaniyaning logistika ehtiyojlariga mos keladigan eng samarali echimlarni taklif qiladi.

3. **5PL (Fifth-Party Logistics) – Beshinchi tomon logistika xizmatlari**
5PL modeli yanada murakkab tizim bo'lib, yetkazib berish zanjiri va elektron tijoratning avtomatlashtirilgan echimlariga asoslangan. Bu turdagi xizmatlar texnologik vositalardan keng foydalanish va raqamli logistika tizimlarini joriy etish orqali samaradorlikni oshiradi.

4. **Freight Forwarding – Yuk tashish ekspeditsiyasi**
Bu turdagi outsorsingda kompaniya yuk tashish jarayonlarini to'liq yoki qisman yuk ekspeditorlariga topshiradi. Ular yuklarni yetkazish, bo'jxona hujjatlarini rasmiylashtirish va transport yo'nalishlarini optimallashtirish bilan shug'ullanadi.

5. **Reverse Logistics – Qaytar logistika xizmatlari**
Ushbu outsorsing turi mahsulotlarni qaytarish, ularni qayta ishlash va utilizatsiya qilish xizmatlarini o'z ichiga oladi. Ayniqsa, elektron tijorat va chakana savdo sohalarida ushbu xizmatga talab yuqori.

Autsorsingning afzalliklari:

- **Mablag'larni tejash.** Outsorsing xizmatining narxi o'zingizda shunday strukturani qurish xarajatlariga qaraganda arzon. Siz xodimlaringizga hisoblangan ish haqiga nisbatan ijtimoiy sug'urtaga ajratma qilishingiz, hamda daromad solig'i ushlab qolishga majbursiz. Outsorser xizmatining qiymati bu sizning xarajatingiz hisoblanib, soliqqa tortiladigan bazani kamaytiradi.

- **Ish o'rnini tejash.** O'zingizda tegishli strukturani yaratish uchun qo'shimcha ofis maydonchasini, orgtexnikani, kanselyariya xarajatlarini, axborot-huquqiy tizimlarini va lisenziyalangan dasturiy ta'minotni talab qilishi mumkin

- **Doimiy uzluksiz ish.** O'z ishchi va xodimlaringizga siz yillik mehnat ta'tili, kasallik nafaqasi berishga majbursiz. Outsorser firma doimiy ishlaydi.

- **Vaqtini tejash.** Kadrlarni tanlash – vaqt talab qiladigan oddiy bo'lmagan masala hisoblanadi. Sizga zarur bo'lgan infratuzilma, texnologiyalar va mutaxassislar bizda yetarlicha mavjud.

- **Kafolatlangan sifat.** Outsorser firma o'z shtatida yuqori malakali mutaxassislar komandasi mavjud va bunday loyihalarni bajarishda boy tajribaga ega.

XULOSA.

Logistika outsorsingi kompaniyalarga vaqt va resurslarni tejash, mijozlarga xizmat ko'rsatish sifatini oshirish va biznesning boshqa yo'nalishlariga e'tibor qaratish imkonini beradi. Kompaniyalar o'z ehtiyojlariga qarab mos logistika outsorsing turini tanlashlari lozim. Raqobatbardosh bo'lish va bozor talablariga moslashish uchun zamonaviy logistika xizmatlaridan samarali foydalanish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Xorijiy davlatlarda outsorsingga berilgan davlat organlari funksiyasini uch guruhga ajratiladi.

Birinchi guruhga ta'minlovchi funksiyalar, masalan, ovqatlantirish, binolarni tozalash, chiqindilarni chiqarish, qo'riqlash xizmati kiradi. Mazkur funksiyalarni osongina outsorsingga berilishi mumkin, chunki bular budget tashkiloti va boshqaruv organlari faoliyatining asosiy vazifalari hisoblanmaydi, ulardan foydalanish nisbatan oddiy standartlashtirilgan hamda ijrochilarga yuqori talablar qo'ymaydi va bilimning yuqori darajasi talab qilinmaydi.

Ikkinchi guruh funksiyalari o'z ichiga ijrochilardan yetarli ravishda yuqori kasbiy malaka talab qiluvchi ta'minlovchi funksiyalarni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu guruh funksiyalari moliya va buxgalteriya, kadrlarni boshqarish, yuridik xizmat, hujjatlar aylanishini ta'minlash, axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanishni qamrab oladi.

Oxirgi yillarda xorijiy davlatlardagi davlat sektoridagi outsorsing, birinchi navbatda, mazkur guruh funksiyalarini bajarish bilan bog'liq, eng ko'p foydalaniladigan outsorsing funksiyalari sifatida axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanishni ko'rsatish mumkin.

Autsorsingga beriladigan uchinchi guruh funksiyalariga davlat xokimiyat organlarining o'zi to'g'ridan-to'g'ri bajaradigan asosiy funksiyalar kiradi, xorijiy davlatlarda bu turdagi outsorsing juda kam uchraydi.

Shunday qilib, mamlakat va mahalliy darajasida budget xarajatlarini optimallashtirish zaruriyati - outsorsingdan foydalanish asosida budget xarajatlarining samaradorligini oshirishdan iboratdir.

Umuman olganda, outsorsingni davlat muassasalari xizmatlariga qo'llashda budget xizmatlarini amalga oshiradigan budget tashkilotlari, tijorat va notijorat tashkilotlarining raqobatbardoshligi hamda budget xarajatlarining natijadorligini oshirish maqsadida outsorsingdan foydalanish maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi.

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